

Impact Response Behavior and Tensile Energy Absorption of Thin CFRP Belt

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SUMMARY: In order to absorb impact energy in a side crashing of automobiles, an impact beam attached inside of doors is useful and its conventional type is made of steel. CFRP belts having lighter weight and higher tensile strength are recently developing instead of steel impact beams.

This paper presents the numerical results of CFRP belts under the impact load. In the FEM analysis, a drop steel weight, rotary pins and the CFRP thin belt were modeled by a 3-D solid element and a 2-D shell element, respectively. The FEM analysis took three contact phenomena into account, namely 1) between the drop weight and the upper belt, 2) between the upper belt and the lower one, 3) between the belt and the rotary pins. The friction coefficient between the belt and the rotary pins was defined as 0.25. This paper also shows the comparison of FEM analysis with the experiment. The experimental strains agreed well with ones obtained by the FEM. Furthermore, it was found that the CFRP thin belt has a potential to be utilized for absorbing impact energy in the side crashing of automobiles.

KEYWORDS: impact, CFRP, energy absorption, experiment, FEM, contact,

INTRODUCTION

In a side collision between automobiles, impact beams equipped inside of doors are useful and their conventional types are made of steel. Furthermore, it is desirable to absorb large amount of collision energy within small deformation because the allowable deformation is limited in the case of side collision. It is generally said that CFRPs are brittle materials and they are considered to be disadvantage ones in the case of absorbing impact energy. However, a high elongation resin is recently developed. If CFRP using this resin as a matrix is broken in a tension mode, the strain energy stored in the CFRP until its brake is expected to be large due to its high tensile strength. In order to progress lighter weight of automobiles, thin CFRP belts are developing instead of steel impact beams. The CFRP thin belt can be transformed the vertical impact force into the axial force of belt as shown in Fig.1

In this paper, the numerical results of CFRP belts under the impact load are shown [1-4]. In the FEM analysis, a drop steel weight, rotary pins and the CFRP thin belt were modeled by a 3-D solid element and a 2-D shell element, respectively. The FEM analysis took three contact phenomena into account, namely 1) between the drop weight and the upper belt, 2) between the upper belt and the lower one, 3) between the belt and the rotary pins. The friction coefficient between the belt and the rotary pins was defined as 0.25. This paper also shows the comparison of FEM analysis with the experiment. The experimental strains agreed well with ones obtained by the FEM. Furthermore, it was found that the CFRP thin belt has a potential to be utilized for absorbing impact energy in the side crashing of automobiles

Fig.1 Energy absorption mechanism of CFRP belt

EXPERIMENT

TEST SPECIMENS: For simulating the side collision, an impact from the drop of weight having mass of 144kg and a head radius of 105mm from height of 1.58m acted on a CFRP thin belt and speed of weight was 20km/sec just before the impact. We used two kinds of CFRP belts, namely one was the CFRP–UD belt composed of a conventional epoxy resin fabricated by means of a sheet winding method. Another belt was composed of a super elongation resin and the same carbon fibers as the former belt and it was fabricated by means of a filament winding method. Their dimensions were decided according to the actual equipment of CFRP thin belts to the inside doors of automobiles. Table1 and Fig. 2 show the dimensions of CFRP thin belts and the experimental apparatuses. The rotary pins (diameter of 40mm) were inserted into the inside of belt at the both ends and the axial load due to the drop weight was measured with a load cell equipped to the side frame. The vertical load was also measured with a load cell equipped to the head of drop weight. Furthermore, the strains were measured on the three positions as shown in Fig.3.

Table1 1 Dimension of CFRP belt (unit: mm)

Mode	CFRP Belt	
	J-01	J-02
Type	80	80
Span	4	5
Width	0.3	0.6
Thickness	3	5
Matrix (Resin)	Epoxy	Super Elongation

Fig.2. Experimental apparatuses

Fig.3 Strain measurement positions

RESULTS: Figs 4 show the strain responses of the position T1 to the time for both CFRP belts. Though they were fabricated with the different method and the matrix, the maximum strain showed almost same value. In the J-01 specimen of conventional epoxy resin fabricated by sheet winding, the difference of strains between the inside and outside surfaces of the position T1 was a few. It means that the J1 belt was

broken by a tensile mode. Otherwise, there was some difference of strains between the inside and the outside of surfaces for the J2 belt because the bending mode was simultaneously appeared due to the larger thickness than the J1.

Fig4-1 Strain response to time for J-01

Fig.4-2 Strain response to time for J-02

FEM ANALYSIS

Time responses including a contact analysis in the FEM were executed by ANSYS ver.5.7. The quarters of CFRP thin belt and drop weight and one of the rotary pins were modeled in the FEM analysis to save computational resource (Fig.5). Since all mechanical properties of CFRP belt composed of the super elongation resin are not still obtained, the CFRP belt composed of the conventional epoxy resin has been analyzed and its mechanical properties are listed in Table 2. The axial direction of the belt was accord to the fiber direction of CFRP. The quarter part of thin belt was divided into 60 in the axial direction and the

	CFRP Belt	Drop Weight & Rotary pin
E_x GPa 1	130	206
E_y GPa 1	8	-
E_z GPa 1	8	-
G_{xy} GPa 1	4	80
G_{yz} GPa 1	4	-
F_x E, θ 1	2.45	-
F_y GPa 1	0.07	-
F_{xy} GPa 1	0.098	-
ν_{xy}	0.34	0.30
Density kg/m^3 1	1600	8000
Structural Element	Elastic Shell	3-D Structural Solid
Contact Element	3-D Target Segment	
Element	3-D Surface-to Surface Contact	

narrow divisions were used near the impact and the support places to avoid a stress concentration. Otherwise, the width direction was equally divided into 6 and the 2-D elastic shell element was used for calculating the CFRP thin belt. The drop steel weight and the rotary pins were divided by three dimensional solids elements. The contact calculation using Target 170 and Conta 173 elements in ANSYS were carried out on three places, namely 1) between the drop weight and the upper surface of belt, 2) between the upper belt and the lower one, 3) between the inside of belt and the rotary pin. The circumferential displacement around the rotary pin could be moved alone and the friction coefficient between the inside of belt and the rotary pin was defined as 0.25.

DISCUSSIONS

STRAIN AND IMPACT LOAD RESPONSES: Fig.6 shows the comparison of experimental results with numerical ones for the strains on the position T1. In which, the experimental data were the plotted with a solid and an open circle symbols until the break of CFRP belt. Otherwise, the numerical ones plotted with an open and solid triangular symbols were calculated until 20msec and these values decreased somewhat after reaching to the maximum value due to the rebounding of weight. Although a small difference between the inside and outside strains could be observed, the experimental strains agreed with the numerical ones and all of strains showed a similar nonlinear response to the time. The comparison of the experiment with the numerical ones is shown in Fig.7, in which a solid and an open circle symbols represent the experimental axial and vertical impact loads, respectively, and an open and solid triangular symbols represent the FEM analysis. The

Fig.6 Comparison of experimental strains to ones obtained by FEM

Fig. 7 Comparison of experimental impact loads to ones obtained by FEM

ESTIMATION OF BREAKTIME: In order to estimate the break time of CFRP thin belts due to the impact load, Tsai-Hill failure criterion

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_L}{F_L}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_T}{F_T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{LT}}{F_{LT}}\right)^2 - \frac{\sigma_L \sigma_T}{F_L^2} = 1 \quad (1)$$

was revised to the following equation because the transverse stress σ_T was very smaller than the longitudinal strength F_L of CFRP.

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_L}{F_L}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_T}{F_T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{LT}}{F_{LT}}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (2)$$

The stress components obtained by the FEM and the strengths of unidirectional CFRP in Table 2 were substituted for Equation 2 and the break time could be obtained when the sum of left terms was over 1, In Table 3, the brake time obtained by the FEM and the time observed in the experiment are listed and these values were very close.

Table 3 Comparison of break time of CFRP belt

	Break time by Exp. (sec)	Break time by FEM (sec)
CFRP Belt	16.4	16.3

ENERGY ABSORPTION: The strain energy absorbed in the CFRP thin belt could be obtained the strain response curve until the break. Fig.8 shows numerical strain response curve on the position T1 and its strain energy per unit volume becomes $5.46 \times 10^7 J$. Since the normalized strain distribution around the

Fig. 8 Strain energy obtained by FEM

CFRP belt divided by the maximum value was not uniform as shown in Fig.9, the strain energy per unit volume was calculated as the average of 6 points around the belt. Then, the total strain energy for the

whole volume of CFRP belt was $558kJ$ and this value became 29.3% of the impact energy due to the dropped weight. Otherwise, the experimental total strain energy obtained from the three points of strain as shown in Fig.3 was somewhat larger than the numerical one and its value became 38.0% of the impact energy.. The absorbed strain energy per unit mass was $21.7kJ/kg$ for the FEM and $28.2kJ/kg$ for the experiment, respectively and these values were effective in comparison with competitive materials of the energy absorption.

Fig.9 Normalized axial strain distribution around belt

CONCLUSIONS

In order to absorb impact energy in a side crashing of automobiles, CFRP thin belts are developing instead of steel impact beams. The main results obtained through this study are summarized as follows:

- 1) The impact vertical load due to the drop weight was efficiently transformed into the axial impact tensile force of CFRP thin belts.
- 2) The FEM results using contact elements showed a good agreement with the experimental results for the strain and impact forces responses of the CFRP thin belt composed of the conventional epoxy resin..
- 3) The experimental and numerical break times agreed well each other. The break time of CFRRP thin belt could be obtained by Tsai-Hill failure criterion and the strengths of unidirectional carbon fiber/epoxy.
- 4) The absorbed strain energy per unit mass was over $20kJ/kg$ and this value was effective in comparison with competitive materials of the energy absorption. It was found that the CFRP thin belt has a potential to be utilized for absorbing impact energy in the side crashing of automobiles.

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